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Effect of Simulation Based Learning on Biology Students' Academic Performance and Retention in Secondary School in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of simulation based learning on Biology students' academic performance and retention in secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State. The study adopted a non-randomized pre-test posttest control group quasi-experimental design. Eighteen thousand six hundred and forty students in 41 co-educational public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis formed the population of the study. Two hundred and sixteen Biology students in four intact classes selected from two schools constituted the sample for the study. Four research question and four hypotheses were posed and formulated respectively to guide the study. The instrument used in data collection was titled "Biology Performance Test". The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the corresponding null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance and t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Results from the study revealed that the mean score of the experimental group was higher than the mean score of the control group. The study also revealed that there was a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control groups. Also, there was a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the male and female students in the experimental group in favour of the male students. It was also found that students taught using the simulation had significantly higher retention of Cell concepts compared to those taught using the traditional lecture method. Therefore, it was recommended that teachers should use stimulation strategy in teaching the concept of Cell. Also, teachers should engage students in an active process of learning through the use of Simulation to create a linkage between what the students already know and the new concept to be learnt.

Keywords: Effect, Simulation Based Learning, Biology Students, Academic Performance Retention

INTRODUCTION

The study of science as a subject that investigates both living and non-living things incorporates biology as the branch that studies the aspects of living things made up of plants and animals. Learning these days can only take place effectively when science and technology are used to impact knowledge to learners through the use of computers with the help of Computer-Aided-Instruction package (simulation) because, science and technology are the main agents of social and economic changes (Umaru (2018). Biology occupies a unique place in school curriculum, biology has been found to be central and related to many subjects such as Botany, Zoology, Medicine, Agricultural science, Nursing, Pharmacy, Biochemistry, etc. As a result of its significance to science, it has drawn the attention of many researchers as observed by

Kareem, (2018). Biology as a science subject cannot be studied in isolation of today's scientific and technological progresses achieved in the use of observation, experimentation, recording, collection of data and its analysis.

Umaru (2018) defined simulation as a program of instruction or a package presented as software for instructional purposes. Several researchers have shown that the use of simulation has positive effect on students' achievement compared to CLM. Taiwo (2018), found that simulation have been used to teach various subjects in Junior Secondary Schools (JSS) and Senior Secondary Schools (SSS). The evolution of Computer-Assisted-Instruction (simulation) shows that simulation has existed for more than 50 years. The first simulation, was a flight simulator for pilots which was designed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in 1950 one of the first application of simulation for educational purposes was developed in 1960s at the University of Illinois called PLATO (Programmed Logic for Automatic Teaching). This program was designed to teach a variety of subjects such as pharmacology, nursing and geometry. In the seventies further developments occurred in computer aided instruction (simulation).

Simulation has been in use for more than five decades for educational purposes; although it is not new in the developed world, it is still new in the Nigerian context. It provides an instructional interaction between the learner and the computer in a variety of contents with or without the assistance of the teacher. It helps learner(s) by presenting the multimedia simulation materials as well as acting as a tutor. It uses the computer to facilitate and improve students' learning through interacting with the computer at their own pace. Simulation directs the learners' attention to different sections in a learning sequence without the direct assistance of the teacher (Petrakis, 2018).

Performance is defined by the oxford dictionary as the attainment of success in educational performance or the act of success in doing something. This determine the extent to which a student or teacher or institution achieves its academic goals. There is no known best method of measuring achievement which normally leads to procedural knowledge, skills, declarative knowledge such as fact. Achievement is commonly measured through tests, examinations or continuous assessments (CA) but in California USA, it is measured by academic performance Steven (2016). Academic performance is usually influenced by individual difference as a result of different level of IQ. Other factors include parental socioeconomic background and physical activities which enhances brain functions such as attention and working memory. Simulation is now the "in thing" for enhanced instruction and achievement in different subjects, biology inclusive.

There is performance feedback immediately based on correct and incorrect responses and lessons are individualized. The rate of learning is paced and controlled by the learner. Learners can review mistakes. simulation programs have assessment and scoring of performance. Simulation and animation environments are provided by the computer. Simulation can be timed to suit the time table needs of class work. Sounds, graphics and colour make it interesting to learners. Tutorials teach a lesson the way teachers give lectures. Instructional games can be simulated (Karren (2018).

Therefore, this study tends to find out if simulation package could be used to improve students' achievement and retention in cell in biology in senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Hence, this study will develop a simulation package on cell and apply it as a teaching strategy to investigate its effectiveness on students' achievement and retention in cell in biology.

Simulation in Education

Simulation had its beginning about 1500 years ago in the game of chess. Two players attempted to simulate a battle between opposing forces. War games ultimately industrialized from this early form of chess. Even though war games have long enjoyed popularity, it was not until the nineteen fifties and sixties that simulation began to be functional to other areas such as business and economics originally, with social sciences following a little later (Jerry & Catherine, 2017).

One would think that with such a long history of use with war games, simulation would have been applied to other disciplines much earlier. However, this method of teaching was not used in public school classrooms until the late 1950s. This was probably due to the long reign of the traditional "rote-memory" methods that persisted into modern times. The behaviorists did little to alleviate the situation by luring students into responding correctly to a given stimulus on the promise of a reward (Jerry & Catherine,

2017). The importance of education was to condition a person to regurgitate information when called upon to do so. Fast forward to age of wide-spread, high-stakes testing, and it would appear, that little has changed in terms of conditioning and regurgitation. In addition to simulating historical events such as debates and mock trials, existing technology has the probable to further change the way teachers simulate learning knowledge across all punishments, and when related with a constructivist approach, technology can meticulously simulate reality and to build rich classroom learning experiences (Hunter, 2015).

Students may be specified a role to play or asked to complete a task in a simulated environment. In any case, the goal is for students to experience the situation from a realistic stand point, apply or practice new skills and knowledge, think critically, and pucker meaning from the scenario. In this paper, simulation is both supported and explored through the cognitivist's belief that people learn in whole circumstances, not by isolated incidences, and therefore, as a teaching method, simulation has the potential to further extend learning through the human factor where an individual's experiences and standpoints have the potential to inspire a given condition or outcome in the classroom setting.

Simulations in education promote the use of critical and evaluative thinking. Because they are ambiguous or open-ended, they encourage students to contemplate the implications of a scenario. The situation feels real, and thus leads students to engage with the activity more enthusiastically and interactively. Simulations in education supports students learn both concepts and how to apply them in a nuanced way in an unanticipated situation. Students often find them more deeply engaging than other activities, as they experience the activity first-hand (Smale, 2016).

Simulations help students appreciate more deeply the management of the environment, politics, community, and culture. For example, by participating in a resource distribution activity, students might gain an understanding of inequity in society. Simulations can reinforce other skills indirectly, such as debating and research skills. Simulations promote the use of critical and evaluative thinking. Because they are ambiguous or open-ended, they encourage students to contemplate the implications of a scenario. The situation feels real, and thus leads students to engage with the activity more enthusiastically and interactively.

Educational Simulation may to a great extent improve learning education, but it is not without consequences (Wiggins, 2016). Firstly, expensive resources and time are required to develop a quality learning experience that uses simulation, also assessment of student learning through simulation is often more complex than with other methods. Simulated experiences are more realistic than some other techniques and they can be so engaging and absorbing that student forget the educational purpose of the exercise. If the simulation has an element of competition, it is important to remind the students that the goal is not to win, but to acquire knowledge and understanding, hence, mindset of the learners must be critically addressed.

Role of Simulation in Instructional Delivery

The positive role of Simulation in Instructional delivery cannot be over-emphasized. Simulations help students learn both concepts and how to apply them in a nuanced way in an unforeseen situation (Wiggins, 2016). Students often find them more deeply engaging than other activities, as they experience the activity first-hand. Simulations help students appreciate more deeply the management of the environment, politics, community, and culture. For example, by participating in a resource distribution activity, students might gain an understanding of inequity in society. Simulations can reinforce other skills indirectly, such as debating and research skills.

Exploring the many ways simulation can be used in instructional delivery, the perspective of international teachers of English language, Hunter (2015) stated that simulation is the act of stimulating the behavior of a situation or a procedure using a suitably analogous phenomenon. Simulation is a teaching technique in which the behavior is not measured, and participants can bring their own experience, knowledge, and skills to the situation and consequently supplement the learning process, change the theoretical setting to a real-life situation, and provide an effective and effectual language learning experience. Simulation can also be careful as a problem-solving activity to which learners bring their own distinct views, feelings, and personalities.

According to Steven (2016), we can classify modeling and simulation activities as practical activities. Their implementation allows teachers to create interactive environments where students can design, create, and test substitute ideas and models that represent a system they observe. The execution of the models allows students to compare the results with their previous perceptions. Resnick (2022) classifies this action as cyclical and iterative, where new ideas generate new creations and new creations create new ideas.

Performing modeling and simulation activities in educational contexts can bring a diverse set of advantages. For Brigas (2019), they are a well-organized and actual tool for teaching and learning complex and dynamic systems. Several authors account that these activities permit more self-motivated, interactive, and motivating learning that can improve the development of skills such as reflection, conclusion making, creativity, and generalization. They also enable learning by discovery.

We can also affirm that the use of simulations, if designed well, can facilitate learning where the student is inspired to develop a scientific attitude, because they permit for creating research environments of real or experimental situations. In this case, students are usually called to 'invest' in determined roles, observing the variables at play and taking responsibility for the development of a given process.

Other studies indicate that the realization of these activities shows that students get better results, such as better transfer of acquired knowledge to real-world situations. This allows the analysis and the representation of phenomena that could be expensive to represent or impossible to visualize. Wilson (2016) also points out that they permit for changing the time scale by compressing it or selecting a part of the time in which a phenomenon occurs. Brigas (2019) point out that they enable students to create stimulating and rich learning environments if access to certain concepts that might otherwise be dangerous and impractical. They also allow for the customization of the pace of learning and repeating experiences as needed.

Despite the potential that exists in introducing these events in an educational context, teachers and students find it difficult to perform modeling and simulation activities. Proof of this is the small number of projects or initiatives that use modeling and simulation as an educational tool. These difficulties of use are due to, among other reasons. The specificities of educational modeling and/or simulation authoring tools, which oblige their users, teachers, and students to have time to adapt to their interface and to have higher-level scientific and technological knowledge than may be the case, the forms of model representation are usually based on quantitative modeling, which compromises their use at educational levels where the fundamental thing is not to know the system in detail but only to have part of it or to have an idea of its functioning, the absence of methodologies that help the teacher implement modeling and simulation activities (Brigas, 2019).

Rationale for Simulation in Teacher Education

Smale (2016) mentioned that simulation system has been utilized at all levels of education ranging from elementary to post graduate studies and in the job training in almost all subject. Developed country have been using simulation for more than three or more decades and lot of research on various aspect of simulation has been conducted in these countries. Hornbil (2014) state that it is important to note that some very strong models of teacher's education provide simultaneous professional development for more than one group. With simulation student often become teacher using the process of peer tutoring. The teacher's role changes to manage and facilitate in many of these situations as the teacher helps the expert communicates with the learners. The teacher also acquires professional development by learning the expert.

Using simulation to increase efficiency in the classroom according to Bull (2015), technology application in classroom may be in area of computer assisted instruction, biology teacher may use the new technologies for words processing, grading, record keeping and lectures. The use of technology in teachers' education to improve classroom efficiency who also supported by other scholars like Freeman (2020).

Types of Simulation Programs:

There are many simulation programs; each simulation program is appropriate under different instructional circumstances, therefore, takes a different pedagogical approach. Although the beginning of simulation was presentation of programmed instruction through computer and the initial simulation program were tutorials, drill and practice and games that were oriented to the behaviorist theories of learning, the new simulation programs are associated solely with a specific learning theories due to sophistication of computer language which has allowed modification of each type of simulation according to any theoretical frame work (Hunter, 2015).

These skill, are usually found in higher intellectual activity. Good drill and practice package provides the user with an enjoyable opportunity for respective interaction and immediate feedback on the accuracy of response. Drill & Practice software is typically associated with behaviorism, because learners are usually given stimuli (questions), are required to make response to the stimulus and then receive some sort of reinforcement.

Tutorials.

Tutorials act like tutors by providing all the information and instructional activities a learner requires to master a topic. All the conceptual or skill based body of knowledge is presented in the screen followed by quiz to assess the comprehension of the concept or acquisition of knowledge. The software monitors the learner's progress on the basis of the results of the quiz taking the user on the new material or back over old material. A good tutorial presentation is enjoyable, thorough and sensitive to the user capabilities; and feed back is immediate as appropriate. Interactivity is key to user involvement and perseverance (Kareen 2018). Tutorial software is more associated with cognitive learning theory because new learning is presented in a systematic way. Students are expected to learn principles and rules, comprehend them and apply newly acquired knowledge to new situations. A computer based tutorial program works with an individual student in a very interactive manner and often provides an ideal learning situation for information transmission.

Process Simulation: This type of simulation speeds up a process, it usually takes long time to complete e.g. seed germination and experimenting with natural laws like the laws of genetics by paring animals with given characteristics and showing the resulting offspring.

Procedural simulation: It teaches the appropriate sequence to perform an experiment or identify the sources of a medical problem or cause of accidents.

Situational simulation: These gives learners a hypothetical situation and ask them to react e.g. buying and selling as in the game "Monopoly" it simulate how to invest in buying and selling.

Games: Instructional games are courseware whose function is to increase motivation by adding game rule to learning activities. They are similar to drill & practice. Fun is expected from Resnick (2019), mentions that simulations are designed as games including role-playing. Learning is built up by discovery, enquiry and decision making. According to Smale (2016), Instructional games are usually associated with behaviorism because of the variety of reinforcement mechanism inherent in game's environments with which students are motivated by competition and game rules to strive to reach the goal.

Problem Solving: This requires the learner to apply higher-order-strategies and synthesize knowledge for multiple curricular areas in order to solve problems. Learners can test hypothesis, learn from mistakes and refine skills as they gain mastery of problem solving techniques.

Retention of Learning

If learners receiving simulation learn better and faster than learners receiving conventional lectures alone, do they retain their learning longer? The answer according to researchers, who have conducted comparative studies of learning retention, is yes. In such researches, learner scores in delayed tests indicate that the retention of content learned using simulation is superior to retention following the traditional lecture methods (Hornbil 2014).

Many factors have been attributed to the underachievement in science subjects by secondary school students in Nigeria and one that is most common is poor teaching methods. Kareen (2018) had earlier observed that the main reason why students are unable to perform well in science education lies with the method of instruction. Teaching methods can best be described as the types of principles and methods

used for instruction. There are many types of teaching methods depending on the skill or information the teacher wants to convey to his students.

Hornbil (2014) observed that the conventional lecture strategy is usually the dominant approach adopted by most science teachers in Nigeria. Teachers do not present the concepts in a variety of contexts for students to understand but in verbal and formal ways using the lecture teaching strategy. Other factors are type of school, lack of academic and professional qualifications, class size, attitude of teachers and students and inadequate motivation of teachers. A teacher who is not properly motivated would be less dedicated to his work and less productive.

At a time when scientific and technological competence is vital to the nation's future, the weak performance of students in science examinations at the secondary schools reflects the uneven quality of current science education at the secondary (upper basic) level of education. Many experts have called for a new approach to science education based on ongoing research on teaching and learning. Several studies have been undertaken on the teaching and learning of science subjects with a view to addressing nature and processes of science, instructional strategies and gender. These efforts were aimed at improving science teaching and learning (Wiggins 2016).

The conventional lecture method is still the most frequently used teaching strategy - usually the dominant approach adopted by most science teachers in Nigeria. The teacher sometimes writes on the chalkboard by way of solving examples or using instructional material while the students listen and take notes. Sometimes they ask the teacher questions for clarification. The method however, does not allow for students' participation as they are not engaged with the topic. They also do not seem to listen for very long thereby leading to minimal retention of concepts. The teacher talks most of the times, leading to, fleeting coverage of numerous topics but without understanding. Wlison (2016) observed that when the conventional lecture strategy is adopted by teachers, students are not actively involved in developing knowledge; they generally remain passive throughout the lesson. Hence, the strategy is mainly a teacher-centered approach to learning.

Gender differences in the Academic performance & Students

Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) is an interactive technique whereby a computer is used to present the material and also to monitor the learning that takes place. Computer Assisted Instruction has been found to be successful and beneficial as instructional approach for boosting interest, uplifting mentality, building up students' retention capacity and performance. Computer Assisted Instruction programs motivate the students and arouse their interest in teaching and learning process even in abstract concepts (Freeman, 2020). In this study, the researcher used computer (laptops), projector screen and software on kinetic theory to teach junior secondary two the concept of kinetic theory of matter.

One of the variables that have been found to affect students' achievement in basic science is gender. Gender issues are of global contemporary concern and gender disparities have been found in students' achievement in basic science examinations. While some researchers are of the view that male students achieve better than the females. Bull (2015) opined that female students achieve better. Yet still, some researchers observed that both male and female students achieve equally. This is an indication that the existing accounts fail to resolve the contradiction between male and female achievement. Therefore, the situation calls for further investigation; more so that it has been opined that instructional method used in the classroom may influence gender and students' academic achievement in science.

The consequence of allowing the aforementioned problems to persist means allowing the gradual decline and fluctuation in the achievement of students in basic science examinations. This will have serious consequences on biology, physics and other science subjects which in turn will affect science and technological development of the nation and the socio-economic life of the nation (Taiwo, 2018). Therefore, there is an urgent need to improve on the teaching and learning of basic science by exploring the use of more innovative learner-centered teaching methods such as the computer assisted instruction. The computer assisted instruction has been used in the teaching and learning of various courses and subject areas with promising results.

Statement of the Problem

Cell is an important topic in secondary school biology curriculum. Research findings have shown that Cell is one of the topics in Biology that students have difficulty in scientific conception which may be attributed to the complex and abstract nature of the concept. West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiners Report, 2020 and 2024 pointed out that students did poorly in questions on Cell in their examinations. The Chief Examiner's reports (2020, 2024) highlighted some of the difficult concepts/topics the candidates performed poorly as: genetics, evolution cell theories, use of microscopes, laboratory rules and management, thus there is a need to proffer solution. Students' faulty conceptions have been identified as one of the major causes of difficulty in students understanding of Cell. Consequently, this academic performance and retention of biology students in secondary schools within Port Harcourt Metropolis have remained a concern with many student struggling to grasp complex concepts like cell. Despite various teaching methods, students' achievement and interest in biology continue to ware. Traditional teaching methods often fall short in engaging students and promoting meaningful learning. This study investigates the effect of simulation-based learning on biology students' academic performance and retention, seeking to determine whether integrating simulations into instruction can enhance students understanding interest and achievement in biology and ultimately improve learning outcome in secondary schools within Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to investigate the effect of computer assisted instruction on biology students' academic performance and retention in secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. find out if there is any difference in the mean performance score of students taught cell using simulation and those taught using lecture methods.
2. Find out the effect of simulation on student' retention ability in the concept of cell relative to those taught with lecture method.
3. find out if there is any difference in the mean performance score of male and female students taught cell using simulation.
4. find out if there is any difference in male and female students' retention ability when taught cell using simulation.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in the mean performance score of students taught cell using simulation and those taught using lecture methods?
2. What is the effect of simulation on student's retention ability on the concept of cell relatives to those taught using lecture method?
3. What is the difference in the mean performance score of male and female students taught cell using simulation?
4. What is the difference in male and female students' retention ability when taught cell using simulation?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of students taught cell using simulation and those taught using lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference in the retention means scores of students taught cell using simulation and those taught using lecture method.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of male and female students taught cell using simulation.
4. There is no significant difference in male and female students' retention ability when taught cell using simulation

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design. Specifically, the non-equivalent, non-randomized pretest-posttest control group design. An experimental design according to Nworgu (2015) is any study in which

the independent variable is manipulated in order to determine its effect on the dependent variable. A quasi-experimental study allows the researcher to control the treatment condition using criteria other than random assignment (Maduabum, 2007). The population of the study comprises all the Senior Secondary School (SSI) students in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State. The total population of this study was 18,640 students (Source Senior Secondary Schools Board, 2023). A multistage sampling procedure was adopted for the study. Two schools was purposively sampled for the study from 41 co-educational public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. The instruments for data collection were a Biology Performance Test (BPT). The instrument has 20 multiple choice test items developed by the researcher. The data collected for the study was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and t-test will be used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Questions 1: *What is the difference in the academic performance of students taught cell using simulation and those taught using lecture methods?*

Table 1 Mean Difference in Performance between Groups

Group	n	pretest		posttest		Mean Difference
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	
Control	93	4.46	1.36	9.30	1.80	4.84
Experimental	123	4.19	1.36	12.42	2.60	8.24
Difference (between)		-0.28		3.12		

Source: Field Survey 2024.

Result as shown in Table 1, shows an improvement in the performance of the students taught cell using simulation. The control group had a mean score of 4.46 on the pre-test and mean score of 9.30 on the post-test with a mean difference (gain) of 4.84. The experimental group had a mean score of 4.19 on the pre-test and a mean score of 12.42 on the post-test with a mean difference (gain) of 8.24. This shows that the experimental group had a higher mean difference of 8.24 as against 4.84 of the control group. The table shows a mean difference (between) of 3.12 in favour of the experimental group

Research Question 2: *What is the effect of simulation on student's retention ability on the concept of cell relatives to those taught using lecture method?*

Table 2: Mean Difference in Retention between Groups

Method	N	Posttest		Postposttest		Retention
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Lecture	93	9.30	1.80	6.78	1.50	-2.52
SIMULATION	123	12.42	2.60	10.27	2.43	-2.15

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The result from Table 2 shows the retention scores in Cell of students taught using simulation and lecture methods. As shown, the simulation group had a mean score of 12.42 at the posttest level and 10.27 at the postpost test level. This is an indication that there was a slight decrease as evident by retention score of -2.15. The posttest mean score of the students taught using lecture method was 9.30 as against postpost test mean score of 6.78. This indicates that there was a decrease of -2.52 in the mean score for this group. This shows that the decrease in mean score between posttest mean score of the lecture method group was higher than that of the simulation group. This suggests that the students exposed to instruction using the simulation teaching approach had a slightly higher retention in Cell than their counterparts exposed to instruction using lecture method.

Research Questions 3: *What is the difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught cell using simulation?*

Table 3: Mean Difference in Performance between Male and Female Students

Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	51	3.73	1.34	13.80	2.07	10.08
Female	72	4.51	1.29	11.44	2.51	6.93
Difference		-0.788		2.359		3.148

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The result from Table 3 shows the mean score in the academic performance of male and female students taught cell using simulation. As shown, the female students had a mean score 4.51 at the pretest level and 11.44 at the posttest level. This is an indication that there was an increase in mean score of the female students, by a difference of 6.93. For the male students, pretest mean score was 3.73 and posttest mean score was 13.80. This is an indication that there was also an increase in mean score of male students taught Cell by a difference of 10.08. This result indicates that the male students had a higher mean gain than the female students. Furthermore, there was a difference in mean score of -0.788 between the female and male students in favour of the female students at the pretest level. At the posttest level, there was a difference in mean score of 2.359 in favour of the male students. This is an indication that the male students performed slightly higher than the female students.

Research Questions 4: *What is the difference in male and female students' retention ability when taught cell using simulation?*

Table 4: Mean Difference in Retention between Male and Female Students

Method	N	Posttest		Postposttest		Retention
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	51	13.80	2.07	11.96	2.38	-1.84
Female	72	11.44	2.51	9.07	1.62	-2.37

The result from Table 4 shows the retention scores in cell of male and female students. As shown, the male students had mean score of 13.80 at the posttest level and 11.96 at the postposttest level. This is an indication that there was a slight decrease as evident by retention score of -1.84. The posttest mean score of the female students was 11.44 as against postposttest mean score of 9.07. This indicates that there was a decrease of -2.37 in the mean score for this group. This shows that the decrease in mean score between posttest mean score of the female students was higher than that of the male students. This suggests that the male students had a slightly higher retention in the understanding of Cell than female students.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean score of students taught cell using simulation and those taught using lecture method.

Table 5: ANCOVA for Difference in Performance between Groups

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	536.390 ^a	2	268.195	51.778	.000	.327
Intercept	2698.086	1	2698.086	520.898	.000	.710
Pretest	20.314	1	20.314	3.922	.049	.018
Method	490.677	1	490.677	94.731	.000	.308
Error	1103.272	213	5.180			
Total	28151.000	216				
Corrected Total	1639.662	215				

a. R Squared = .327 (Adjusted R Squared = .321)

Result from Table 5, indicate $F(1, 213) = 94.731, p < 0.05$, based on this the hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference between the mean score of students taught cell using simulation and those taught using lecture method.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant different in the retention means scores of students taught cell using simulation and those taught using lecture method.

Table 6: t-test for Difference in Retention between Groups

Method	posttest			Postpost test		Retention	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
	N	Mean	SD	Mean	SD					
Lecture	93	9.30	1.80	6.78	1.50	-2.52	214	1.357	0.00	Rejected
Simulation	123	12.42	2.60	10.27	2.43	-2.15				

The result in table 6 shows the t-test for test of hypothesis two. As shown, $t(df=214) = 1.357, p = 0.00 < 0.05$. Based on this, the hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference in the mean retention score of students when taught Cell using the simulation and lecture method.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean score of male and female students taught cell using simulation.

Table 7: t-test for Difference in Performance between Male and Female Students

Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Difference	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD					
Male	51	3.73	1.34	13.80	2.07	10.08	121	-5.52	0.000	Rejected
Female	72	4.51	1.29	11.44	2.51	6.93				
Difference		-0.788		2.359		3.148				

The result in Table 7 shows the t-test for test of hypothesis three. As shown, $t(df=121) = -5.52, p < 0.05$. Based on this, the hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference in the mean performance of male and female students when taught Cell using the simulation.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the mean score of male and female students' retention ability when taught cell using simulation.

Table 8: t-test for Difference in Retention between Male and Female Students

Method	N	Posttest		Postposttest		Retention	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD					
Male	51	13.80	2.07	11.96	2.38	-1.84	121	1.427	0.156	Accepted
Female	72	11.44	2.51	9.07	1.62	-2.37				

The result in Table 8 shows the t-test for test of hypothesis four. As shown, $t(df=121) = 1.427, p > 0.05$. Based on this, the hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there was no significant difference in the mean performance of male and female students when taught Cell using the simulation.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first research question sought to ascertain the difference in the mean scores of students taught Cell with the Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) approach and those taught using the traditional teaching method in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result showed that students exposed to instruction using the simulation performed better than those exposed to instruction in Cell using the traditional lecture method. The test of hypothesis one showed that there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students taught Cell with the Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) approach and those taught using the traditional teaching method in secondary schools in

Port Harcourt Metropolis. This result agrees with the result of Hunter, (2015) who investigated the effects of computer assisted instruction (simulation) on secondary school students' performance in Biology in Oyo State. The findings of the study showed that the performance of students exposed to simulation were better than their counter parts exposed to conventional lecture methods

The second research question sought to find out the difference between the retention scores of students taught Cell with the Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) approach and those taught using the traditional teaching method in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result showed that students exposed to instruction using the Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) approach had a slightly higher retention in Cell than their counterparts exposed to instruction using lecture method. The test of hypothesis two showed that there was a significant difference in the mean retention score of students in Cell when taught using the Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) approach and lecture method (Karren, 2018).

This result further buttresses the result of the first research question and hypothesis. As the students exposed to instruction in Cell had significant higher performance than their counterparts exposed to same instruction through lecture method, so also their retention was higher. This result is in consonance with the findings of Umaru (2018) who carried out a study to investigated the Impact of Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) on the Performance of Senior Secondary School Biology Students in Katsina Metropolis. The study revealed that the simulation method aroused the interest of the learners and improves retention of the concept taught and hence improves academic performance of the learners.

The third research question sought to determine the difference between the mean scores of male and female students taught Cell using the Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) approach in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result showed that the male students had a higher mean gain than the female students. The further indicated that the male students performed slightly higher than the female students. The test of hypothesis two showed that there was no significant difference in the mean performance of male and female students when taught Cell using the Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) approach. This result shows that the slight difference between performance of male and female students which was in favour of the male students may have just been by chance.

The fourth research question sought to determine the difference between the retention scores of male and female students taught Cell using the Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) approach in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result showed that there was a decrease in the mean score between posttest mean score of the female students and the decrease was higher than that of the male students. This is an indication that the male students had a slightly higher retention in the concept of Cell than female students. The test of hypothesis four showed that there was no significant difference in the mean retention between male and female students taught Cell using the Computer Assisted Instruction (simulation) approach. This suggests that the simulation approach is gender friendly in terms of students' retention ability.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn. The Simulation al approach teaching approach significantly improved students' performance in Cell compared to the traditional lecture method. This improvement suggests that simulation enhances clarity and understanding of complex concepts like Cell. It was also concluded that male students had slightly higher performance than female students when taught using the simulation, but this difference was not statistically significant, indicating that the simulation is a gender-friendly teaching method suitable for both male and female students. It was further concluded that students taught using the simulation had significantly higher retention of Cell concepts compared to those taught using the traditional lecture method. This suggests that the simulation promotes deeper understanding and longer-lasting learning. Finally, it was concluded that male students showed significantly higher retention in the concept of Cell than female students when taught using the simulation. This indicates that while the simulation benefits all students, male students may retain the concepts slightly better over time.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Teachers should employ the Simulation al approach in teaching Cell and other science topics as it has the capability to enhance students' understanding and performance in complex concepts.
2. Stakeholders in the educational sector, such as Ministry of Education, Schools Board and school heads should promote the simulation as a gender-inclusive method of instruction, to ensure that both male and female students benefit equally from its utilization.
3. Schools should implement the simulation in teaching to improve students' retention of concepts, especially in subjects requiring long-term recall, such as STEM
4. Teachers should explore supplementary strategies, such as personalized feedback and reinforcement, to support female students in achieving better retention of concept of Cell when using the Simulation al approach.

REFERENCES

- Adelekun, C.B. (2016). Active learning: Creating excitement in the classroom. ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Report No. 1. Washington, D.C.: The George Washington University, School of Education and Human Development.
- Bull, A (2015). Girls and science. *International Association for Evaluation of Educational Achievement Monograph*, 17(9), 306-310.
- Freeman, J. D. (2020). A twelve-year longitudinal study of science concept learning. *Americana Research Journal*. (28) 117 - 153
- Hornbil, L. (2014). Should we be worried? What the research says about gender differences in access, use, attitudes, and achievement with computers. *Educational Technology*, 38 (4), 56 – 60.
- Hunter, L. (2015). Enhancing student's academic performance in biology through practical activities. *Americana Research Journal*, 11(9), 66-73.
- Jerry, B. & Cathering, T (2017). The influence of teacher preparation and use of instructional materials on primary school pupils' performance in integrated science. *Ilorin Journal of Education*, 12(3), 67 - 88.
- Kareem, A. (2018). The effects of simulation on Jordanian college students' achievements in an introductory computer science course. *Electronic Journal for the Integration of Technology in Education*, 5, 17 – 24.
- Patrakis, J. (2018): The role of practical activities in improving student's academic achievement in biology. *Journal Science Education and Technology*, 5(4), 159-165.
- Smale, O. (2016). Students' attitude to the use of computer for learning and achievement in biological concept. *Journal of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria*, 27 (2), 61 – 65
- Steven, M. (2016). A view of the research on the efficacy of SIMULATION. *Electronic Journal for the Integration of Technology in Education*, 1 (2), 43 – 58.
- Taiwo, A. (2018): *The relative effectiveness of computer assisted and text- assisted programme instruction on students learning outcomes in social studies*. Unpublished PhD thesis of the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Umaru, B. T (2018). The influence of teacher preparation and use of instructional materials on primary school pupils' performance in integrated science. *Ilorin Journal of Education*, 12, 56 - 64.
- Wilson, R. (2016). *A comparison study of the learning effectiveness of computer aided instruction vs classroom lecture*. Retrieved December 22, 2007, from http://www.concentric.net/~Walwpr/thesis/4_result.html
- Wiggins D. (2016). Longitudinal study of science concept learning. *Americana Research Journal*. (28) 117 - 153